

Linnæus University

Monthly Report February 2025

SENTINEL Wild Birds

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SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. The data in this report are based on previously unpublished samples collected from November 2024 to February 2025, along with backlogged samples from Georgia dating back to August 2024.

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report (published on 30th of January 2025; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14772852>), and as of 15th February 2025, test results have been submitted for 4296 samples taken from 2518 individual wild birds representing 29 taxa across six nodes in Europe (Table 1). Of the 4296 collected samples, 1781 (41 %) were cloacal swabs, 1679 (39 %) tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 649 (15 %) faecal samples, 115 (3 %) feather samples, 52 (1 %) combined swabs (choana + cloacal), 19 (<1 %) pooled organs, and one (<1 %) blood sample. Of all samples, 513 (11.9 %) from seven different taxa were positive for avian influenza virus, of which none were positive for highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus (Figure 1; Table 2).

The overall bird-level prevalence of avian influenza virus in these recently submitted samples was 17.5 %. The highest bird-level prevalence was found in Sweden (30.3 %; Table 1), and among the most frequently sampled birds, Mallard had a prevalence of 27.6 % (409 of 1484 individuals), Eurasian Teal 5.9 % (20 of 341 individuals), sentinel domestic Mallard 3.9 % (5 of 128 individuals), Pochard 2.7 % (2 of 77 individuals), and Black-headed Gull and Marbled Duck 0 % (0 of 174 and 0 of 123 individuals, respectively) (Table 1).

TABLE 1 Total number of individuals sampled in the wild (including recaptures of some birds), as well as number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza in the respective country. The table includes previously unpublished samples from August 2024 to February 2025.

Group/species	Node 2 Sweden		Node 2 Lithuania		Node 4 Georgia		Node 6 Austria		Node 6 Switzerland		Node 6 Germany		Node 7 Italy		Node 8 France		Node 9 Spain		Total			
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.		
<i>Waterfowl</i>																						
Barnacle Goose	1	0																		1	0	
Brent Goose	9	0																		9	0	
Duck <i>spp.</i>											2	0								2	0	
Mallard	893	274			545	133	2	1	15	0	2	0	1	0	21	1	5	0	1484	409		
Sentinel domestic Mallard					128	5														128	5	
Gadwall					1	0			5	0										6	0	
Pintail					16	0														16	0	
Shoveler					3	0											1	0		4	0	
Eurasian Wigeon	1	0							1	1										2	1	
Marbled Duck																	123	0		123	0	
Eurasian Teal	25	8			143	3	1	0	2	0			114	0	56	9				341	20	
Garganey					16	3														16	3	
Pochard					65	1	8	1												73	2	
Red-crested Pochard																	2	0		2	0	
Ferruginous Duck					12	0											40	0		52	0	
Tufted Duck					5	0	3	0												8	0	
Common Scoter			1	0																1	0	
Velvet Scoter			1	0																1	0	
Long-tailed Duck					2	0														2	0	
<i>Grebes</i>																						
Great Crested Grebe					1	0	2	0													3	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																						
Great Cormorant							1	0													1	0
Pygmy Cormorant					1	0															1	0
<i>Raptors</i>																						
Common Buzzard	1	0																			1	0
<i>Rails</i>																						
Common Moorhen																			13	0	13	0
Eurasian Coot					16	1	8	0											20	0	44	1
<i>Larids</i>																						
Gull <i>spp.</i>											5	0									5	0
Black-headed Gull					151	0					23	0									174	0
Common Gull			1	0							1	0									2	0
European Herring Gull			3	0																	3	0
Total	930	282	6	0	1105	146	25	2	23	1	33	0	115	0	77	10	204	0	2518	441		

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FIGURE 1 Sample sites for the 2518 birds sampled in nine European countries, yielding 513 samples positive for avian influenza virus. The figure includes previously unpublished samples from August 2024 to February 2025.

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TABLE 2 Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus, in the respective country. The table includes previously unpublished samples from August 2024 to February 2025.

Group/species	Node 2 Sweden			Node 2 Lithuania			Node 4 Georgia			Node 6 Austria			Node 6 Switzerland			Node 6 Germany			Node 7 Italy			Node 8 France			Node 9 Spain			Total					
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI			
<i>Waterfowl</i>																																	
Barnacle Goose	2	0	0																									2	0	0			
Brent Goose	18	0	0																									18	0	0			
Duck spp.																2	0	0										2	0	0			
Mallard	1676	339	0				757	137	0	4	1	0	15	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0	42	1	0	10	0	0	2509	478	0			
Sentinel domestic Mallard							200	5	0																			200	5	0			
Gadwall							2	0	0				5	0	0													7	0	0			
Pintail							27	0	0																			27	0	0			
Shoveler							5	0	0																2	0	0	7	0	0			
Eurasian Wigeon	2	0	0										1	1	0													3	1	0			
Marbled Duck																									243	0	0	243	0	0			
Eurasian Teal	47	11	0				188	3	0	2	1	0	2	0	0	342	0	0	112	9	0							693	24	0			
Garganey							18	3	0																			18	3	0			
Pochard							96	1	0	10	0	0																106	1	0			
Red-crested Pochard																									4	0	0	4	0	0			
Ferruginous Duck							24	0	0																80	0	0	104	0	0			
Tufted Duck							6	0	0	3	0	0																9	0	0			
Common Scoter				1	0	0																						1	0	0			
Velvet Scoter				1	0	0																						1	0	0			
Long-tailed Duck							2	0	0																			2	0	0			
<i>Grebes</i>																																	
Great Crested Grebe							2	0	0	2	0	0																			4	0	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																																	
Great Cormorant										3	0	0																			3	0	0
Pygmy Cormorant							2	0	0																						2	0	0
<i>Raptors</i>																																	
Common Buzzard	2	0	0																												2	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																																	
Common Moorhen																									26	0	0	26	0	0			
Eurasian Coot							31	1	0	8	0	0													40	0	0	79	1	0			
<i>Larids</i>																																	
Gull spp.																5	0	0													5	0	0
Black-headed Gull							191	0	0							23	0	0													214	0	0
Common Gull				1	0	0										1	0	0													2	0	0
European Herring Gull				3	0	0																									3	0	0
Total	1747	350	0	6	0	0	1551	150	0	32	2	0	23	1	0	33	0	0	345	0	0	154	10	0	405	0	0	4296	513	0			

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A weekly compilation of all 8034 samples (positive and negative; including previously published), collected at each node from August 2024 to February 2025, can be seen in Figure 2.

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FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of samples collected at each node, as well as all nodes combined, from week 34, 2024 to week 7, 2025. In total, 8034 samples (negative samples in blue; avian influenza virus-positive samples in orange) have been collected at seven nodes between August 2024 and February 2025, yielding 929 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 22 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on 30th of January (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14772852>), and as of 15th February 2025, a total of 19 new sequences have been generated from samples positive for H5 avian influenza viruses. All 19 samples were collected from Mallards in Sweden (Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea), of which H5N2 (N=6), H5N3 (N=11) and H5Nx (N=1) subtypes were detected. Genetic analysis of the haemagglutinin (HA) gene sequences from 18 of these samples found that they belonged to the Eurasian non-Goose Guangdong (EA-nonGsGd) low pathogenicity avian influenza (LPAI) clade. For the final sample, the HA sequence was not recovered, and the subtype was inferred from PCR testing, therefore the clade cannot be determined. The majority of the HA gene sequences from these samples, showed similarity to H5N2 and H5N3 LPAI viruses previously detected at Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (see November 2024 report):

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<https://zenodo.org/records/14507721>), as well as sequences from across Europe and Asia (Figure 3, Group 1). However, one of the HA sequences did not cluster with the other sequences collected from this node and grouped with sequences from Europe only (Figure 3, Group 2). This could be suggestive of two distinct incursions of similar, yet distinct H5 LPAI viruses into the wild bird population being sampled within Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea.

The Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea

FIGURE 3 Phylogenetic analyses of the HA sequences generated by Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea. Image of a subset of the HA tree displaying the sequences from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea. The two phylogenetic groups are indicated.

In addition to the H5 genome sequences, a further 38 non-H5 genome sequences were generated from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea. All of these samples were collected from Mallards in Sweden, and as seen in the previous report (see January 2025 report: <https://zenodo.org/records/14772852>), wide subtypic diversity was observed (5 x H1N2, 1 x H4N3, 1 x H4N4, 10 x H4N6, 1 x H4N9, 3 x H6N8, 1 x H10N3, 5 x H10N4, 1 x H11N6, 8 x H11N9 and 2 x HxN3).

3. CONCLUSION

The number of analysed samples has more than doubled since the last published report in January 2025, with the majority originating from Sweden and Georgia. With nearly all samples collected in 2024 now analysed, the peak prevalence (76.2%) was observed in week 37 (week from 9 September 2024). However, this peak is based on a relatively small sample size (42 samples, of which 32 tested positive for avian influenza virus). A second peak occurred in week 45 (week from 4 November 2024), with a prevalence of 29.2% (849 samples collected, of which 248 tested positive for avian influenza virus). These peaks are primarily based on samples collected from Mallards in Sweden. Positive detections of avian influenza virus in Mallards are common in Sweden, particularly at Ottenby, where the wild bird trap is located, during autumn migration. While the proportion of positive samples is relatively high, the number of HPAI cases has so far been low, with only 22 confirmed cases in 2024, all in Eurasian Teals in Italy.

Although there is a slight backlog of samples collected in 2025, the overall prevalence remains low at 1.4%, with no confirmed cases of HPAI virus.

We thank the fieldworkers, laboratory personnel, and node coordinators in all participating countries for their essential contributions to sample collection, laboratory work, and coordination. Their efforts are crucial to this project.
